

Identification of Invasive Alien Species using DNA barcodes

Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
Rue Vautier 29,
1000 Brussels, Belgium
+32 (0)2 627 41 23

Royal Museum for Central Africa
Leuvensesteenweg 13,
3080 Tervuren, Belgium
+32 (0)2 769 58 54

General introduction to this factsheet

The Barcoding Facility for Organisms and Tissues of Policy Concern (BopCo) aims at developing an expertise forum to facilitate the identification of biological samples of policy concern in Belgium and Europe. The project represents part of the Belgian federal contribution to the European Research Infrastructure Consortium LifeWatch.

Non-native species which are being introduced into Europe, whether by accident or deliberately, can be of policy concern since some of them can reproduce and disperse rapidly in a new territory, establish viable populations and even outcompete native species. As a consequence of their presence, natural and managed ecosystems can be disrupted, crops and livestock affected, and vector-borne diseases or parasites might be introduced, impacting human health and socio-economic activities. Non-native species causing such adverse effects are called Invasive Alien Species (IAS). In order to protect native biodiversity and ecosystems, and to mitigate the potential impact on human health and socio-economic activities, the issue of IAS is tackled in Europe by EU Regulation 1143/2014 of the European Parliament and Council. The IAS Regulation provides for a set of measures to be taken across all member states. The list of Invasive Alien Species of Union Concern is regularly updated. In order to implement the proposed actions, however, methods for accurate species identification are required when suspicious biological material is encountered.

Because morphology-based species identifications are not always possible (e.g. cryptic species, trace material, early life-stages), the purpose of the present work is to investigate and evaluate the usefulness of DNA sequence data to identify each of the IAS included in the EU Regulation. The results are presented as factsheets (one per IAS) compiled using publicly available DNA sequence data and information aggregated from various sources. Each factsheet consists of two major parts; (i) a short introduction to the specific IAS compiling information on its taxonomy and current occurrence/distribution in Europe; (ii) an investigation with respect to the usefulness of publicly available DNA sequences to identify this IAS to the taxonomic level stated in the EU list using DNA barcoding. For further information about the reasoning behind the applied approach and details on the materials and methods utilised, please see below and Smitz *et al.* [1].

More info about BopCo on <http://bopco.myspecies.info/> or contact us via bopco@naturalsciences.be.

More info on the EU Regulation on http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/invasivealien/index_en.htm.

Ludwigia grandiflora

(Michx.) Greuter & Burdet, 1987

Common names:

English: water primrose, (perennial, large-flower, Uruguayan) primrose-willow

French: jussie à grandes fleurs, ludwigie à grandes fleurs

German: großblütiges Heusenkraut

Dutch: grote waterteunisbloem

Last update: November 2018

General information on *Ludwigia grandiflora*

Classification

Kingdom	Phylum	Clade	Order	Family	Genus
Plantae	Magnoliophyta	Eudicots	Myrtales	Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia</i>

Species in the same genus: N = 82-91 [2-4]

Note: Zadini *et al.* [5] separated two 'chromosomal entities' within a variable species then called *Ludwigia uruguayensis*, elevating these to two closely related species: *L. grandiflora* and *L. hexapetala*, which was confirmed by morphological studies. The two species are known to hybridize.

Infra-species level: N = 0-2 [6]

Note: Some authors argue that the split between two species in the note above should be treated as subspecies instead.

Native range: [5]

South America; (northeast) Argentina, Bolivia, Paraguay, Uruguay.

Invasive range: [7, 8]

Europe (geographical):

Belgium, France, Germany, Ireland, Netherlands, Spain, Switzerland, United Kingdom.

For more detailed locality information and the most recent distribution updates, please visit:

<https://www.gbif.org/species/5421039>

<https://gd.eppo.int/taxon/LUDUR/distribution>

<http://alien.jrc.ec.europa.eu/SpeciesMapper>

<http://www.europe-aliens.org/speciesFactsheet.do?speciesId=9756#>

Outside Europe (geographical):

Kenya, United States of America.

Morphology, biology, invasion, negative effects and remedies

For more information on *Ludwigia grandiflora* please see the references and online information listed at the end of this document.

Species identification based on DNA barcodes

Introduction

DNA barcoding is a species identification method that uses a short genetic sequence (DNA barcode) to compare an unknown sample to a database of reference sequences with known species affiliations. The underlying rationale is that the divergence of nucleotide sequences among different species is larger than the nucleotide divergence between sequences within a species. DNA barcoding can facilitate the identification of IAS samples, especially when morphological characteristics are absent or useless. To assure correct species identifications, however, reference libraries need to include a sufficiently large number of sequences of (i) the IAS under investigation, in order to assess the intraspecific genetic divergence; (ii) the closely related species, in order to evaluate the interspecific genetic divergence; (iii) the different geographical areas covering the distribution range (native and invasive) of the IAS in order to detect potential population structure or local hybrids.

Against this background, BopCo evaluated the inclusion of the IAS and their close relatives in both publicly available reference libraries BOLD (www.boldsystems.org/) and GenBank (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/) to estimate the reliability with which a species identification can be obtained using DNA barcoding.

Material and Methods [1]

Download all sequence data available for the genus

Filtering the data and selecting 'promising' markers

Aligning and trimming of the sequences

Building Neighbour-Joining tree with Bootstrap support

Conclusion:

Based on the present evaluation of the available sequence data, no marker can reliably identify *Ludwigia peploides*. Full ITS seem most promising to further investigate once new sequence data becomes available.

Discussion

DNA markers for which *Ludwigia* sequences were available, were downloaded from GenBank and BOLD for all represented species of the genus *Ludwigia*. Four DNA markers were evaluated (Table 1). Considering all markers investigated, at best one third of the species in the genus *Ludwigia* are represented (Table 2). The now unaccepted species *L. uruguayensis* was not encountered as such in the online reference databases, the new, correct species names are already applied (above notes). Whenever sequence data was available for *L. hexapetala* there was no clustering with *L. grandiflora*.

The ITS regions (full ITS, as well as ITS1 and ITS2 regions separately) are available for ca. 30 *Ludwigia* species (Table 2). The full ITS marker appears to have potential to distinguish among the *Ludwigia* species since the NJ-tree shows a high level of well-supported clustering, but *L. grandiflora* is not yet represented. Only for ITS2 one partial *L. grandiflora* sequence was available. This is still insufficient to assess the ability of the full ITS region, ITS1 or even ITS2 to identify *L. grandiflora*. Additional sequences for *L. grandiflora* and the missing congeners would allow to better evaluate the potential of the ITS regions to distinguish *L. grandiflora* from related species.

For both universal barcode markers **rbcl** and **matK**, as well as the **trnH-psbA** intergenic spacer many sequences are available for *L. grandiflora*, but the markers show little genetic variation among the different species, resulting in non-clustering. The low genetic variation raises doubts about the taxonomic resolution of these markers for the genus *Ludwigia*.

For the **trnL-trnF** and **atpB-rbcl** intergenic spacers, **phyC gene** and **rpl32** no *L. grandiflora* sequence data is available and/or the markers show little genetic variation among the few represented species. Therefore it is currently impossible to assess the ability of these markers to identify *L. grandiflora*.

Table 1: Overview of the encountered issues concerning the DNA-based identification of the IAS [1]: (1) Insufficient publicly available DNA sequences of the IAS to capture the intra-species divergence; (2) Poor geographical coverage of the IAS sequences (native or invasive range missing); (3) The IAS sequences do not form supported clusters; (4) Potential misidentification of a specimen which influences the clustering of the IAS sequences; and (5) Not all congeneric species are represented in the final NJ-

tree. An 'X' indicates that the issue was encountered, a '1' indicates only one *L. grandiflora* sequence was available, n/a: not applicable.

Markers analysed	1	2	3	4	5
rbcl			X		X
matK	X		X		X
full ITS	X	X	n/a		X
ITS2	X	X	1		X
trnH-psbA			X	X	X

Table 2: Publicly available sequences downloaded (November 2018) from BOLD and GenBank which were withheld as reliable and informative in the final alignment that was used for building the NJ-trees. The species names follow [3]. The list of species is limited to those members of *Ludwigia* for which at least one sequence was used in any of the NJ-trees. An 'X' indicates that at least one sequence was used in the final alignment, '(X)²' indicates only ITS region 2 was available for analysis.

Species in genus	rbcl	matK	ITS(2)	trnH-psbA
<i>Ludwigia adscendens</i>	X	X		X
<i>Ludwigia affinis</i>			X	
<i>Ludwigia alata</i>			X	
<i>Ludwigia alternifolia</i>	X	X		X
<i>Ludwigia arcuata</i>	X	X	X	
<i>Ludwigia brevipes</i>			X	
<i>Ludwigia curtissii</i>	X	X	X	
<i>Ludwigia decurrens</i>			X	
<i>Ludwigia erecta</i>	X	X		
<i>Ludwigia foliobracteolata</i>			(X) ²	
<i>Ludwigia glandulosa</i>	X	X		X
<i>Ludwigia grandiflora</i>	X	X	(X)²	X
<i>Ludwigia helminthorrhiza</i>			X	
<i>Ludwigia hexapetala</i>	X	X	(X) ²	
<i>Ludwigia hyssopifolia</i>	X		X	
<i>Ludwigia inclinata</i>	X		X	X
<i>Ludwigia lanceolata</i>			X	
<i>Ludwigia leptocarpa</i>	X	X	X	
<i>Ludwigia linearis</i>	X	X	X	
<i>Ludwigia linifolia</i>	X	X	X	
<i>Ludwigia maritima</i>	X	X		
<i>Ludwigia microcarpa</i>	X	X	X	
<i>Ludwigia nervosa</i>	X	X	X	
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i>	X	X	X	X
<i>Ludwigia ovalis</i>	X	X	X	
<i>Ludwigia palustris</i>	X	X	X	X
<i>Ludwigia peploides</i>	X	X	X	X
<i>Ludwigia perrium</i>	X			
<i>Ludwigia peruviana</i>	X	X		X
<i>Ludwigia pilosa</i>	X	X		
<i>Ludwigia polycarpa</i>	X	X	X	
<i>Ludwigia prostrata</i>	X	X	X	
<i>Ludwigia ravenii</i>			X	
<i>Ludwigia repens</i>	X	X	X	X
<i>Ludwigia rigida</i>			X	
<i>Ludwigia sedioides</i>	X		X	X
<i>Ludwigia simpsonii</i>			X	
<i>Ludwigia spathulata</i>			X	
<i>Ludwigia sphaerocarpa</i>			X	
<i>Ludwigia suffruticosa</i>	X	X		
<i>Ludwigia torulosa</i>			X	
<i>Ludwigia virgata</i>	X	X		
TOTAL species	29 /82-91	25 /82-91	29 (32)² /82-91	11 /82-91

For a more elaborate discussion of the available databases, the sequence selection process, the outcome of the NJ-tree analyses, the usefulness of the investigated DNA sequences for species identification, as well as information on how to send samples for analyses please contact BopCo directly.

References and online information

Online information

https://www.codeplantesenvahissantes.fr/fileadmin/PEE_Ressources/RTE/RE_1143_Ludwigia_grandiflora.pdf
http://www.q-bank.eu/Plants/Controlsheets/Ludwigia_grandiflora_office_guide.pdf
http://www.q-bank.eu/Plants/Factsheets/Ludwigia_grandiflora_EN.pdf
<https://secure.fera.defra.gov.uk/nonnativespecies/downloadDocument.cfm?id=460>

Picture credits

Page 1: Waterteunisbloem, flower By jan parie [CC BY-NC-SA 2.0]
Page 2 (center): *Ludwigia grandiflora* in Botanical Gardens, Madison By Krzysztof Ziarnik, Kenraiz [CC BY-SA 4.0]
Page 2 (left insert): *Ludwigia grandiflora* in Saint-Mathurin-sur-Loire By Olivier Pichard [CC BY-SA 3.0]
Page 2 (right): *Ludwigia grandiflora* 10681, Seed from multi-seeded dry fruit By The Groningen Institute of Archaeology, Digital Seeds Atlas of The Netherlands [All Rights Reserved] Permission sought directly from the copyright holders.

References

- [1] N. Smitz, S. Gombeer, K. Meganck, A. Vanderheyden, Y. R. Van Bourgonie, T. Backeljau, and M. De Meyer, "Identifying IAS based on DNA barcoding using currently available sequence data: details on applied material and methods." 2019. [Online]. Available from: <http://bopco.myspecies.info/content/invasive-alien-species-ias-factsheets>.
- [2] P. F. Stevens, "Angiosperm Phylogeny Website," *Version 14*, 2001. [Online]. Available: <http://www.mobot.org/MOBOT/research/APweb>. [Accessed: 14-Mar-2018].
- [3] "The Plant List. Version 1.1," *Published on the Internet*, 2013. [Online]. Available: www.theplantlist.org/. [Accessed: 15-Feb-2018].
- [4] E. M. Zardini, C. Peng, and P. C. Hoch, "Chromosome Numbers in *Ludwigia* sect. *Oligospermum* and sect. *Oocarpon* (Onagraceae)," *Taxon*, vol. 40, no. 2, pp. 221–230, 1991.
- [5] E. M. Zardini, H. Gu, and P. H. Raven, "On the Separation of Two Species within the *Ludwigia uruguayensis* Complex (Onagraceae)," *Syst. Bot.*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 242–244, 1991.
- [6] G. L. Nesom and J. T. Kartesz, "Observations on the *Ludwigia uruguayensis* complex in US.pdf," *Castanea*, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 123–125, 2000.
- [7] A. Mikulyuk, "*Ludwigia grandiflora* (water primrose)," *CABI Invasive Species Compendium*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cabi.org/ISC/datasheet/109148>. [Accessed: 07-Nov-2018].
- [8] GBIF Secretariat, "*Ludwigia grandiflora* (Michx.) Greuter & Burdet," *GBIF Backbone Taxonomy*, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.15468/39omei>. [Accessed: 07-Nov-2018].

To cite this factsheet, please use

Barcoding Facility for Organisms and Tissues of Policy Concern, 2019. Factsheet on *Ludwigia grandiflora*; November 2018. In: Identification of Invasive Alien Species using DNA barcodes. BopCo, Belgium. Available from: www.bopco.myspecies.info/content/invasive-alien-species-ias-factsheets, accessed on DD-MM-YYYY.

DISCLAIMER: The information represented in this factsheet has been compiled from many different sources. Every reasonable effort has been made to ensure that the material presented is accurate and reflects the current (see date last update) scientific knowledge. However, recent changes in e.g. taxonomy and distribution, or the publication of additional reference sequences may not be implemented. The views which are expressed in the "Conclusion" are those of the author(s) and have not been peer-reviewed. BopCo does not guarantee the accuracy of the data included in this factsheet. The content of the factsheet is for information only and is not intended as legal advice. BopCo may not be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein. If you should notice any issues considering the content of this factsheet, or if you would like to contribute any additional information to it, please contact us through bopco@naturalsciences.be.

